

Is it possible to harmonize the SOC measurement? Results of the 1st Eurasian GLOSOLAN PT (2023/2024)

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Soil organic carbon (SOC) is a system of specific and non-specific organic compounds. There is no consensus on the nature and origin of humic substances (HS) in soils [1]. The development of modern methods expands the understanding of the structure of humic substances, but the initial stage of their characterization is the measurement of SOC. The problem of comparability of SOC values obtained by different methods remains and can be solved by harmonizing them. The National Reference Laboratory of the Russian Federation in the GLOSOLAN system (FAO) (<https://ib.komisc.ru/rusolan/>) for 25 laboratories from six countries conducted the 1st Eurasian professional tests (PT) for measuring SOC using various methods: reference – Dry combustion on an elemental C, N-analyzer (DC) [3]; Tyurin (T) and Walkley-Black (W-B) methods with photometric termination [2] and the method for measuring the loss of mass on ignition of soil (LOI). The analysis of the results of PT allowed us to draw the following conclusions.

1. The established permissible relative error of SOC measurements by the dichromatometric method equal to 20%, as well as the introduction of correction factors in the T and W-B methods equal to 1.15 and 1.3, respectively, allow obtaining harmonized measurement results by any of the three methods: DC, T and W-B. It is necessary to develop a reliable method for converting SOC obtained by the LOI method taking into account the factor 0.58 with other analytical techniques. Otherwise, comparison of SOC measured by this method with the results of other methods should be carried out with great caution.

2. The factors reducing the accuracy of SOC measurements by the T and W-B methods were identified:

- correctness of the assessment of the characteristics of the calibration function;
- selection of the sample of the analyzed soil. The criterion for selecting the soil mass is the compliance of the optical density of the solution obtained after SOC oxidation with the optimal value from 0.05 to 0.5;
- a method for separating the solid and liquid phases after oxidation of the carbon of organic compounds with potassium dichromate. Centrifugation is a priority for separating the phases of the mixture;
- it is recommended to recalculate SOC for an absolutely dry sample of soil. Fluctuations in room humidity cause a relative shift in SOC of an air-dry sample from an absolutely dry one of the same sample by up to 6%.

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References

1. Zavarzina A. G., Danchenko N. N., Demin V. V., Artemyeva Z. S., Kogut B. M. Humic substances: hypotheses and reality (a review) // Eurasian Soil Sci. 2021, 54, 1826-185.
2. Metodika izmereniy massovoy doli ugleroda organicheskikh soyedineniy i organicheskogo veshchestva fotometricheskimi metodami (metody Tyurin i Walkley-Black) / № 88-17641-001-2020 / Ye. Vanchikova et al. Syktyvkar, IB Komi NTS UrO RAN. 2020. 51 s.
3. Metodika izmereniy massovoy doli azota, ugleroda, organicheskogo veshchestva na elementnom analizatore YEA 1110 (CHNS-O) / № 88-17641-004-2016 / Vanchikova Ye. et al. Syktyvkar, IB Komi NTS UrO RAN. 29 s.